

Study of outcome of pediatric shaft of femur fracture treated with Titanium elastic nailing system

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Abstract: Femoral shaft fractures account for 1.6% of all infant skeletal injuries and are incapacitating. The treatment of these fractures is mostly determined by the patient's age, fracture pattern, related traumas, physique, and family's financial situation. We assessed the use of the elastic stable intramedullary nail (ESIN) and its consequences in the surgical therapy of femoral shaft fractures in children. From June 2018 to June 2019, fifty-two youngsters were treated with titanium elastic nails (TEN) at our Janaki Medical College Teaching Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal. At the conclusion of the investigation, 48 children were present. According to Winquest and Hansen's classification, fractures were classified as Grade I (n=32), Grade II (n=10), and Grade III (n=6); compound fractures were classified as Grade I (n=5) and Grade II (n=3). 36 midshaft fractures, 7 proximal third shaft fractures, and 5 distal third shaft fractures were observed. The final results were analyzed clinically using Flynn's criteria and radiologically using the criteria of Anthony et al. The average length of follow-up was 20 months (range 12 – 40 months). Radiologically, all fractures healed with grade III callus production between 9 and 12 weeks (mean 9.7 weeks). Using Flynn's criteria, the findings were determined to be excellent for 40 children (83%) and satisfactory for 8 children (17%). Nail end-caused soreness in the soft tissues close to the knee was the most common condition in our study (25%). Other problems include limb amputation (n=5), Varus malunion (n=4), infection at the nail protrusion site (n=4), and nail migration (n=2). No delayed union, non-union, or refractures occurred. In appropriately selected youngsters, TEN is a minimally invasive, safe, and relatively simple treatment for fracture shaft of femur.

Keywords: Femoral diaphyseal fractures; Pediatric; Titanium elastic nailing.

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Introduction

Orthopedic doctors treat femoral shaft fractures as one of the most frequent serious pediatric injuries. In the pediatric population, they account for 1-2% of all fractures(1). Age-related treatment has historically been influenced by the fracture's kind, location, and other accompanying injuries. The majority of pediatric femoral shaft fractures can be successfully treated conservatively by immobilization in a spica cast, either either away or following a period of traction, due to quick healing and spontaneous correction of angulation(2, 3). When conservative techniques are unable to achieve or maintain an adequate reduction of the fracture, an open fracture, a patient with a head injury, or numerous injuries, surgical stabilization becomes necessary. Pediatric femoral shaft fractures can be surgically stabilized using a variety of

techniques, including stiff intramedullary nailing, compression plating, and external fixation. (4, 5, 6, 7, 8) Infections in the pin tract, loss of reduction, refracture following implant removal, growth stop, and avascular necrosis of the capital femoral epiphysis were all issues and consequences connected to these procedures. (9)

Regarding how younger kids (often under 5 years old) and adults (> 16 years) should be treated, there isn't much debate. There are numerous surgical and nonsurgical therapy options available for kids between the ages of 5 and 16; however, the optimal course of action is not universally agreed upon. 10 When early closed reduction and a spica cast are employed, individuals in this intermediate age range are more likely to experience shortening and malunion than younger children. Additionally, the negative effects of protracted immobility have motivated the use of surgical methods that allow for quick mobilization. Therefore, operational stabilization becomes necessary when conservative treatments fail to achieve or maintain a satisfactory reduction of the fracture. Since it was first used to treat femoral fractures in 1979 by the Nancy group, elastic stable intramedullary nailing (ESIN) has grown in popularity.(11) They are load-sharing devices that can bend without having to cross the physis during insertion because of their flexibility. With this minimally invasive procedure, early ambulation is possible within 48–72 hours and only relatively small incisions are needed for hardware installation and removal, giving it a cosmetic benefit over other traditional surgical techniques. The best option for stabilizing pediatric long bone fractures is still this treatment due to its positive outcomes and lack of major side effects. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness and acceptability of using elastic nails to treat juvenile femoral fractures.

Research Methodology

52 kids between the ages of 6 and 16 were treated at our institution, according to a retrospective check of hospital records, of which 48 were reachable for follow-up. The information gathered covered the patient's characteristics (age, gender), a description of the fracture (type, location, pattern), the type of surgery performed (open or closed), the presence of fracture angulation or rotational malalignment, specifics regarding the union of the fracture from the initial X-ray to the final follow-up X-ray, and rehabilitation milestones (non-weight bearing, partial and full weight bearing, return to school), as well as the presence of any complications. In our study, the average age of the 30 boys and 18 girls was 9.5 years (with a range of 6 to 16 years) at the time of injury.

Road traffic accidents were the most frequent cause of injury (n = 34, 70%), followed by falls from a height (n = 14, 30%). There were 36 fractures in the middle third, seven in the proximal third, five in the distal third, and 28 on the right side (58%) and 20 on the left (42%). According to the AO classification, there were four different types of fracture patterns: 32-A3 (n=24), 32-A2 (n=12), 32-A1 (n=6), and 32-B3 (n=6). According to Winquest and Hansen's classification, fractures were categorized as Grade I (n=32), Grade II (n=10), and Grade III (n=6). 7 patients had associated injuries, including 3 patients with minor head injuries, 4 patients with associated upper limb fractures, 2 patients with fractures of both forearm bones on the right side, 1 patient with type I epiphyseal injury on the right side of the distal radius, and 1 patient with type I monteggia fracture on the left side. Five open fractures of grade I and three of grade II were present. After thorough pre-op evaluation, all cases were scheduled for surgery within 10 days (mean 3.6 days). For our study, we had inclusion and exclusion standards.

Standards for admittance.

Children aged 6 to 16 years old who have fractures that are either closed or of grade I or grade II openness.

Exclusion conditions

children younger than 6 years old and older than 16 years old, children with open fractures of grade III or pathological fractures, children with metabolic bone disease, children who are unable to walk, children who have neuromuscular disorders, and children with segmental and severely comminuted fractures of grade IV.

Technique

Following the administration of a preventative antibiotic, the kid was given a localized anesthetic and then laid supine on a fracture table with the injured limb adducted by one hundred degrees. The arms of the F-tool were re-adjusted

depending upon the fracture configuration and the bulk of the thigh. Alignment was confirmed in both planes by an image intensifier and was used to make an entry for the placement of skin incision and dividing the fascia-lata in most cases. Closed reduction was performed by manual traction and gentle rotation along with the use of the F-tool, which is a radiolucent device. Closed reduction was performed by manual traction and Only in cases in which the fracture was located in the distal third or in which the cortex distally was observed to be comminuted did we adopt an antegrade entry method to hold the distal nail entry site. During the procedure, nail caps were not placed on any of the patients' nails.

We used two nails with the same diameter, which was determined using the pre-operative radiograph by the following formula:

1. According to the method used by Flynn et al., the diameter of the nail is calculated by multiplying the width of the nail at its narrowest point with 0.4 millimeters (8).
2. According to the Kasser and Beaty calculation, nail size equals the internal diameter divided by 0.5 mm (9).

Fixed in length, nails are available in five diameter sizes ranging from 2.5mm to 4.5mm. For the purpose of identification, the nails are color coded. The drill was angled at a 10 degree angle, and the tip of the nail was likewise bent in order to aid placement and to allow the nail to bounce off the opposing cortex when it was being inserted.

Two nails were driven all the way up to the fracture site, and in order to avoid any angulation at the fracture site, it is important that both nails penetrate through the fracture site almost simultaneously. We performed minor open reduction in ten of the situations. Nails were driven further into the proximal fragment to diverge laterally towards the greater trochanter and medially within the femoral neck so that early mobilization was possible. The nails were placed in a double "C" construct to ensure three-point fixation, and for proper rotational stability, nails were driven further into the proximal fragment (7). It was ensured that the nails would not penetrate the growth plate in either the proximal or distal direction. At the point where the nail entered the cortex, it was trimmed so that only one centimeter of the nail now projects beyond the cortex. It was important to limit the amount of bending that was done in order to minimize impingement and bursa concerns. In two of the cases, which is 4% of the total, there was cock screwing of the nails, and we amended it intraoperatively.

Antibiotics were administered intravenously for a total of three days after the surgery. On the ninth day after surgery, the sutures were removed. There was no postoperative external immobilization applied, and patients were allowed to begin progressive mobilization. The children were monitored at intervals of one, two, three, and six months until their fractures had healed. At each visit, the progression of union at the fracture site was evaluated radiologically, the tenderness at the fracture site was determined by clinical examination, and limb alignment, rotation, length discrepancy, range of motion of the hip and knee, as well as any other complications, were also taken into account. After a scan indicated a soft callus at the fracture site, the patient was allowed to begin bearing their full weight. At the end of six months and at the end of one year, the children underwent clinical evaluations according to Flynn's criteria [Table 1] and radiological evaluations according to Anthony et al criteria [Table 2] respectively (8, 10).

Table 1: Flynn’s Criteria

Variables	Excellent result (n= 40, 83%)	Satisfactory result (n= 8, 17%)	Poor result (n= 0, 0%)
Length discrepancy	<1cm	<2cm	>2cm
Mal-alignment	5 degrees	5 to 10 degrees	>10 degrees
Pain	No	No	Yes
Complications	None	Minor and solved	Major and/or residual morbidity

Table 2: Anthony Radiological Criteria

Grade 0	No identifiable fracture healing
Grade 1 (Average callus formation at 3.6 weeks)	Primary bone healing with little or no periosteal new bone formation
Grade 2	Periosteal new bone formation on two sides of the femur
Grade 3 (n= 48, Average callus formation at 9.7 weeks)	Periosteal new bone formation on three or four sides of the femur

Results

The average length of the operation was 65 minutes (range 40-90 minutes). In our study, there was no post-operative infection even in open fractures, and the average hospital stay was 7.3 days (ranging from 5 to 15 days). The hospital stay was greater in children with head traumas and associated additional ailments. The median body weight was 27.5 kg, the average BMI was 27.2, and the mean age was 9 years (range: 6 to 16 years) (range 24.4 to 31.0). According to Flynn and Beaty's formula, the minimum nail size utilized was 2.5mm, while the highest nail size used was 4mm.

A callus was initially noticed on a follow-up radiograph at a mean of 3.6 weeks in the 48 children who were available for evaluation, with a mean follow-up of 20 months (range 12 to 40 months) (range 3.2-6.4 weeks). All fractures in our study healed to a grade III callus in an average of 9.7 weeks (9–12 weeks), at which point full weight bearing and school attendance were both commenced [Table 3]. In an average of 8.6 weeks, the knee's functional range of motion was attained (6 – 14 weeks). At the end of the follow-up, clinical assessment found that all patients had complete range of motion in their hip, knee, and ankle.

Intra-operative	Postoperative	Leg-length discrepancy
Difficulty/loss of reduction(10)	Nonunion/delayed union(0)	Shortening (5)
Rods exchanged/improper size selection (2)	Re-fracture(0)	<1 cm(4)
Penetration of proximal cortex(0)	Nail tip irritation(12)	<2 cm(1)
Cock screw phenomenon(2)	Malalignment(4)	>2cm(0)
Blood loss (0)	Asymptomatic nail migration(2)	Lengthening (0)
	Pin site infection(4)	
Total-14	Total -22	Total -5

Anthony et al criteria were used to evaluate radiological data. After 12 weeks, grade III calluses were present on all of the kids. Two kids who had head injuries had substantial, very early callus formation that diminished with time, and the outcome was great. In our investigation, there were no nonunion or delayed unions. Flynn's criteria were applied throughout the clinical evaluation. Results were good for eight children (17%) and outstanding for 40 children (83%) [Case 1- Figures Figures11-4]. [Case 2-Figures 55- -10]. 10]. No kid received a subpar grade.

Skin irritation and impingement caused by the distal nail ends were the most frequent issues in our current investigation, occurring in 12 patients (25%) [Table 4]. In two cases (4%), we observed asymptomatic nail migration [Case 3-Figures 3-Figures1111- -14]. 14]. The solution to all of these issues was nail removal. Out of 48 cases, five (10%) experienced limb length shortening, with four children having a minor shortening of less than 5 mm. One child who suffered a comminuted fracture and weighed 65 kg at the age of 14 had a 15 mm shortening. An angle of more than 100 in the coronal plane or more than 150 in the sagittal plane was considered to be angular mal alignment (11). Four children in our study (8%) developed varus malunions with a coronal angle of greater than five degrees. If a rotational misalignment exceeded 10 degrees, it was considered "extreme." There were none of our kids that had rotational malalignment. Four kids (8%) had nail protrusion site infections, which were treated with oral antibiotics and a daily dressing.

FIGURE: Proximal third shaft of femur fracture.

The orthopedics community has struggled to find a solution to the age-old question of which treatment option is the most appropriate for femoral shaft fractures. The fact that non-operative treatment can result in complications such as malunion, joint stiffness, and a delay in functional recovery in older children, as well as prolonged hospitalization, which can cause a financial loss for the family, and an increased hospital bed occupancy ratio, has led to the development of operative fixation for fractures of this type (13, 14).

TEN is an elastic stable intra-medullary nail that functions according to the principle of symmetric bracing action of two nails with the same modulus of elasticity. This gives three point fixation, rotational, axial, transitional, and bending stability by counteracting the distraction and compression forces that are working at the fracture site (15, 16).

Within twelve weeks of having their fractures fixed, all of the fractures in this series healed completely without any instances of non-union or delayed union. When compared to other children, those that had a transverse fracture pattern healed more quickly and weighed more than the others. When compared to female children, male children got married at a younger age on average. Oh et al noted that none of the 31 fractures in his study had any signs of delayed union after healing for a period of 12 weeks (17). According to a study conducted by Buechsenchuetz et al., in 42 patients who were treated with ESIN, all fractures healed at a mean of 88 days after the initial injury (18).

Because of TEN, the amount of time patients needed to spend in the hospital has significantly lowered. In the current series, the average time away from school was 7.3 days, and students went back to class 9.7 weeks after their absence ended, which caused less disruption in the children's ability to continue their education. In this series, the average time for partial weight bearing was 4.5 weeks, while the average time for complete weight bearing was 9.7 weeks. In children who had a comminuted fracture, a head injury and other traumas that were connected with it impacted the patients' mobility, which in turn delayed the patients' ability to bear weight. Oh et al. employed ender nails and observed patients walking without the assistance of any assistive equipment at a mean of 9.7 weeks (17). Walking without the need of assistive equipment was observed in patients who were receiving TENs by Flynn et al. and Mazda et al. at an average time of 8.5 and 9.5 weeks, respectively (1, 19). The indication for TEN is growing as its benefits become more widely understood and it is found to have a significantly lower risk of problems as compared to other methods of fixation. The most significant benefits are that they are not expensive and can be obtained easily in a variety of diameters.

Because we only included children whose periosteum was still intact in our study, we were able to determine that the functional outcomes of open and closed femoral shaft fractures were comparable. Additionally, because TENS does not disturb the fracture hematoma when the procedure is performed as a closed procedure, the risk of infection is significantly reduced. There is a reduced risk of avascular necrosis of the femoral head when the procedure is performed in a retrograde way (20, 21).

Our outcomes were stated to be outstanding in comparison to those of previous studies after rigorous evaluation of the nail size employing the formula that was employed. In the series conducted by Narayanan et al., a smaller and/or mismatched nail diameter was employed in three of the patients, which was related with an increased incidence of malrotation and varus or valgus angulation.

The geometry of the fracture as well as its placement are crucial factors that determine the outcome of surgical treatment. In our investigation, TEN offered outstanding results in transverse, short oblique fractures. According to Flynn et al. and Narayanan et al., TEN is appropriate for fractures that are transverse, short oblique, and minimally comminuted. [Citation needed] (1, 22).

In comparison to other studies, ours found that the risk of entrance site irritation was the most common problem encountered (25%) among those who participated in the study. Out of 123 cases, Ligier and colleagues found that nail protrusion was the cause of 13 instances of skin ulceration or a local inflammatory reaction (23). Within the context of our study, this complication may have been prevented by appropriately selecting the insertion location and appropriately advancing the nail to lie against the supracondylar flare. In this current series, we had two patients who experienced nail migration, which most likely occurred as a result of improper technique. Karaoglu et al. found that there were two instances of proximal migration among the series of 31 femoral fractures that were secured with ender nails (24).

Because we utilized two nails of the same thickness after performing the necessary pre-bending, we only experienced four instances of Varus angulation. This issue may have been prevented with sufficient bracing. This enlightens us that when treating unstable fracture patterns and fractures in obese children, a cautious approach is always required (25-27). Therefore, it is possible to correct this misalignment through the application of further plaster stability, through traction, through a brief period of bed rest, or through the utilization of a femoral brace. In five of the cases, there was an abnormality in the limb's length, and three of those cases exhibited angulation at the fracture site. A few more years of follow-up are going to be needed before it will be possible to ascertain the exact difference in the lower limb limbs. According to the findings of our research, four out of the ten participants had a superficial infection at the nail projecting location, which could have been a result of improper hygiene practices. We experienced per-operative technical issues in ten of the cases where we attempted closed reduction but were unable due to the presence of soft tissue interposition. As a result, we had to open the fracture site. This could be the result of incorrect traction or splinting, or it could be the

result of concomitant injuries that caused a delay in surgery. In two different instances, we observed the cork screw phenomena, which the picture intensifier was able to deduce and then replace in the appropriate manner.

In this study, we assessed the clinical significance of our findings by applying Flynn's criteria. We had adequate results with 8 children (17%) and great results with 40 children (83%) who participated in the study. We did not have any outcomes that were below par. Our findings are comparable to those found in previous research that followed a process that is analogous to the one used by Flynn et al. and Narayanan et al (1, 22). Within the scope of our research, onycholysis was performed at the conclusion of a year as an outpatient treatment under general anesthesia. There were no complications either during or after the procedure.

Due to the fact that this study was conducted in a single location, it is important that the findings not be generalized without using extreme caution. We did not investigate any other methods of fixing in addition to TEN. The treatment's long-term effects were not investigated in any detail.

TEN is a successful treatment for fracture femur in appropriately selected children with a relatively low risk of sequelae. It is minimally invasive, safe, and provides physical protection. It is also reasonably simple to apply. The majority of the difficulties are in reality caused by faulty technique, which is something that can be remedied by following to the fundamental principles and technical features in a stringent manner. The use of transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) in children aged 6 to 16 years old for the treatment of femoral shaft fractures speeds up the healing process, reduces the amount of shortening and mal-union, and enables earlier rehabilitation and return to school life with improved functional outcomes. For fractures of the femoral shaft in youngsters, we offer TEN as a treatment option.

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